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Consistent modelling and testing theory of high effectiveness heat exchanger performance by means of Shannon 1948 entropy

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Abstract

The components of the Hot Balance of Plant (H-BoP) of SOFC and SOEC (r-SOC) systems are in fact energy quanta managers. They organize the exchange of quanta in a well ordered way with heat exchanging processes or catalytic supported chemical conversions. Examples for stationary and mobile applications like electrical busses are Air Preheaters, Anode OffGas Coolers, Fuel Steam Humidifier, Fuel Reformers. Because considerations based on thermodynamics entropy could not offer a satisfactory explanation, a more fundamental definition of entropy based on the Shannon 1948 entropy is applied. A Shannon Isentropic Heat Exchanger shows insight in the formulation coming from Kays & London (1964) for compact heat exchangers. Starting from the laminar heat exchange model, it is enlarged towards heat exchangers with enhanced heat transfer due to micro-turbulences. A mathematical and graphical approach is discussed. A testing methodology is developed that offers the advantages to identify and quantify the performance quality accurately, and enables to discover links with the causes of performance degradation. A generalization towards catalytic supported reactions in the heat exchanger is touched to demonstrate the similarities. This approach delivers a clear different view on the thermodynamics in a high effectiveness heat exchanger, which can be characterized as a result of “thinking out of the box”.

Introduction

Until now the performance of high temperature counter-flow heat exchangers is mainly approached over the First Law of Thermodynamics (FLT) and the effectiveness definition which led in some cases to confusion and discussions in communications about expected performances. By start using the Second Law of Thermodynamics (SLT) and the notion entropy, a new approach and definitions are generated to facilitate communication regarding this matter.

Figure 1. Basic scheme of counterflow heat exchanger.

The basic scheme of a counter-flow heat exchanger shows two separated flows, a hot flow (highest inlet temperature T_3) that provides heat and a cold flow (lowest inlet temperature T_1) that receives heat. Hot flow travels on the top from left to right. Cold flow is traveling on the bottom from right to left. Effectiveness is defined as how close the target temperature is reached:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{T_{cold,out} - T_{cold,in}}{T_{hot,in} - T_{cold,in}} \quad [1]$$

Scientific Approach

A to the essence reduced non-dimensional model with no phase change is developed. This model is based on the following basics. According the thermodynamic approach, the following equations yield:

1) the continuity equation: “mass in” is “mass out”.

$$\int_A \rho \cdot v \cdot dA = 0$$

2) the first law of thermodynamics (FLT): conservation of energy. What disappears in the hot flow has to appear in the cold flow. The heat exchanger is considered as perfectly insulated, an adiabatic heat exchanger. In practice this means that the heat loss to the outside of the heat exchanger is significantly lower than 1% of the heat exchanging power between the hot flow and the cold flow.

$$\int_A \rho \cdot v \cdot h \cdot dA = 0$$

3) the second law of thermodynamics (SLT). Entropy always increases over time. When a quantum leaves the hot flow, entropy reduces with a quantity equal to the ratio of the quantum energy divided by the absolute temperature where it leaves the hot flow. The quantum travels through the system to end up in the cold flow where it increases the entropy with a value equal to the ratio of the same quantum energy divided by the absolute temperature at that place, which is lower from where it started in the hot flow. Thus overall entropy increased.

$$ds_{hot} = \frac{dq}{T_{hot}}$$

$$ds_{cold} = \frac{dq}{T_{cold}}$$

$$dq = c_p \cdot \delta T$$

Well Managed Quanta Travel Schemes

It is wrong to assume that all the heat is provided at the same quality. You have to consider that the heat at the hot side inlet T3 is a pile of quanta, going from low temperature up to the high temperature. In figure 2, the inlet is set on the left side, outlet on the right side, the hot flow on the top, the cold flow below.

Figure 2. Quanta travel scheme H=0.

The resolution of this pile is arbitrary, at least 2 or higher. We select an arbitrary resolution of the quantum pile, assume here 10. We look at the situation where we have one quantum left in the hot outlet, which means that you have 9 quanta into the cold outlet according the first law of thermodynamics FLT.

The rule of the game is that each quantum can be used for a lower level, but not an equal or higher level. This is due to the thermal resistance $1/k$ of the main heat exchanging surface (3).

$$\frac{1}{k} = \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_1} + R_{f,1} \right) \cdot \frac{A_2}{A_1} + R_{wall} + \frac{1}{\alpha_2} + R_{f,2} \quad [2]$$

This means level 9 on the cold side can only be delivered by level 10 from the hot side. It also explains that we cannot get rid of level 1 on the hot side because there is no lower level available on the cold side.

Furthermore, because we have to transfer level 2 from the hot side, we need to use it for level 1 on the cold side.

However, level 2 from the hot side is not accessible. Nature reacts as if we only have access to the quantum on the top of the pile. So you have to put the quanta in a kind of register to have access to level 2 from the hot side and then build up the quanta on the cold side with the eldest quantum on the bottom and the youngest on the top.

This illustrates that these Hot BoP components work as quantum managers with well defined structure.

Shannon 1948 Entropy

Now the information theory of Shannon 1948 is introduced (1). Shannon defined the entropy H as the following two equations.

$$H = - \sum_{p_i} p_i \cdot \log_2(p_i) \quad [3]$$

with $\sum p_i = 1$

All cases must be considered so that the sum of all probabilities is one, and H is a summation of values of a function only depending on the probability itself of that case. The Shannon 1948 entropy is related to the amount of missing information. How many questions do I have to pose to solve the problem? Let us calculate the Shannon 1948 entropy of this situation.

Here we see that there is only one way to solve this situation, with the given rules of the game, thus the probability p_i is one, $p_i=1$. A second case does not exist. If we calculate the Shannon entropy $H=1 \cdot \log_2(1)$ is zero. Shannon entropy is zero.

Although the Shannon entropy dH is a mathematical formulation out of the Information Theory, it reveals to be more basic than the definition of entropy in Thermodynamics ds . The link between both can be demonstrated by applying some straight forward mathematical operations. By using Lagrange multipliers, we are able to find the condition with maximal disorder on the distribution of any set of energy holders or containers E_i . This leads to the link between Shannon and the Boltzmann distribution.

1. $\sum_i(p_i) = 1$
2. $\sum_i(p_i \cdot E_i) = \langle E \rangle = \text{average energy} = \text{constant}$

$$L = H + \alpha \cdot \left(\sum_i p_i - 1 \right) + \beta \cdot \left(\sum_i (p_i \cdot E_i) - \langle E \rangle \right)$$

$$L = - \sum_i (p_i \cdot \ln(p_i)) + \alpha \cdot \left(\sum_i p_i - 1 \right) + \beta \cdot \left(\sum_i (p_i \cdot E_i) - \langle E \rangle \right)$$

$$\frac{dL}{dp_1} \rightarrow \ln(p_1) + \frac{p_1}{p_1} + \alpha + \beta \cdot E_1 = 0$$

$$\frac{dL}{dp_i} \rightarrow \ln(p_i) + 1 + \alpha + \beta \cdot E_i = 0$$

$$\ln(p_i) = -1 - \alpha - \beta \cdot E_i$$

$$p_i = K \cdot e^{-\beta \cdot E_i}$$

$$K = e^{-1-\alpha}$$

$$\beta = \frac{1}{k \cdot T} \quad \text{or} \quad T = \frac{1}{k \cdot \beta}$$

This distribution is linked with our definition of temperature. By further using differentiation techniques, one ends up with the link between dH and ds , being the Boltzmann constant:

$$dH = \beta \cdot d\langle E \rangle = \frac{d\langle E \rangle}{k \cdot T}$$

$$ds = \frac{dE}{T} = k \cdot \frac{dE}{k \cdot T} = k \cdot dH$$

Back to the heat exchanger formula's for ideal counter-flow heat exchanger [4] or H=0 "Shannon Isentropic heat exchanger" out of literature of Kays and London or VDI-Wärme Atlas, effectiveness is expressed as a function of NTU and z.

$$\varepsilon_{ideal,z=1} = \frac{NTU}{NTU + 1} = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{T_3 - T_1}$$

$$\varepsilon_{ideal,z<1} = \frac{1 - e^{[(z-1).NTU]}}{1 - z \cdot e^{[(z-1).NTU]}} = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{T_3 - T_1}$$

$$NTU = \frac{k \cdot A}{(\text{massflow} \cdot C_p)_{cold}}$$

$$z = \frac{(\text{massflow} \cdot C_p)_{cold}}{(\text{massflow} \cdot C_p)_{hot}}$$
[4]

The value z is the ratio of the thermal capacities of the flows determined by the product of mass-flow and c_p . The value z shows the effect of one quantum on the change in temperature in the hot flow and the cold flow. At $z=1$, the effect on temperature on both sides is the same. When z deviates from one, the effect on temperature increment is different.

NTU stands for Number of Transfer Units (2). It gives a relation between the main heat exchanging surface and the thermal capacity of the cold flow. Because we arbitrary selected a resolution of 10, we were able to transfer 9 units resulting in an effectiveness of 90%. If we arbitrary select a resolution of 2, we can only transfer 1 unit resulting in an effectiveness of 50%. This is fully in line with the formula's out of literature saying:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{NTU}{NTU + 1}$$
[5]

We put this behavior in figure 3. Y-axis is the effectiveness. X-axis is the reciprocal value of NTU, giving a non-dimensional mass-flow.

The right side is a high mass-flow and/or a rather small heat exchanger. The left side is low mass-flow and/or a very big heat exchanger.

Line $z=1$ is the behavior of the "Shannon Isentropic heat exchanger" in balance. At $NTU=1$ half of the pile (50%) remains in the hot flow resulting in an effectiveness=50%. At $NTU=9$ one tenth (10%) of the pile remains in the hot flow resulting in an effectiveness=90%. At $NTU=19$ one twentieth (5%) of the pile remains in the hot flow resulting in an effectiveness=95%. So each scheme is linked to a specific NTU-value on the X-axis.

Figure 3. Effectiveness as a function of NTU at z=1.

Additional graphs are shown in figure 4 for multiple z-values. High effectiveness can easily be reached if more heat is available on the hot side (mass-flow or c_p), thus at z-values lower than 1. High effectiveness cannot be reached if less heat is available on the hot side (mass-flow or c_p), thus at z-values higher than 1. However, for all the points in figure 4 the Shannon 1948 entropy is zero: $H=0$. For each value of NTU the structured scheme of the quanta travel paths remains valid as discussed above. Only due to the changed value of z, the temperature scale for the cold outlet is no longer linear with the number of quanta.

Figure 4. Effectiveness as a function of NTU for multiple z-values.

Quanta Travel Schemes with Amount of Disorder

What happens now in case where we could exchange nine quanta NTU=9, but only exchange 7, leaving 3 at the exit of the hot flow? This is correct according the first law of Thermodynamics. Now we have more possibilities to reach this result. For instance one could use 10 for 1, 9 for 2. From here onwards we do not have any choice. Because 4 has to go to the cold side, we have to use 4 for 3. The rest has to follow to come to the end result. But we could also start using 9 for 1, 10 for 2. Or we could use 8 for 1, 6 for 2 and so on. This results in multiple ways to come to this result.

Figure 5. Quanta travel scheme $H <> 0$.

Figure 6. Shannon 1948 entropy contribution per case.

If we calculate the Shannon 1948 entropy now assuming we have 25 cases, (notice there are much more cases) all with equal probability, we have to look in figure 6 at the x-axis with $p_i = 1/25 = 0.04$ resulting in a function value of 0.2. We have to sum this value over all the cases resulting in $25 \times 0.2 = 5$. Conclusion, the entropy increased.

Figure 7. Performance chart of real heat exchangers with $z=1$.

If we integrate the previous case with $NTU=9$ in a performance chart of real heat exchangers with $z=1$ as shown in figure 7, we start from the Shannon curve out of figure 3 and identify the point with the structured exchange at 90% effectiveness down to 70% effectiveness according the red arrow.

Figure 8. Structured Shannon heat exchanger embedded in 6 conductances G (green lines).

We composed a model with in the center a “Shannon Isentropic heat exchanger”, managing the quanta in a well structured way, embedded in six resistors, called G , linking all the ports of the “Shannon Isentropic heat exchanger” with each other. In this way quanta are able to travel in an unstructured way around the well structured core, for instance from $T3$ to $T1$ ($10 > 1$) or other possibilities. For the simplicity all the resistors are given the same conductance value G . Because G is a thermal conductance, just as $k.A$, the ratio of both results in the non-dimensional quality parameter $(k.A/G)$. Now we do the math based on the continuity equation and first law of thermodynamics, and calculate the temperatures upstream and downstream of $T1$, $T2$, $T3$ and $T4$, expressing them as $T'1$, $T'2$, $T'3$ and $T'4$. To avoid transcendent calculations, it is assumed that the temperatures given by the “Shannon Isentropic heat exchanger” determine the quantum over the conductance G . If one deviates very far from the “Shannon Isentropic heat exchanger”, this simplification does not longer hold. For the case where G is zero, thus the quality factor $(k.A/G)$ infinite, we end up in the Shannon $H=0$ case. All graphs with higher entropy are situated below this graph. The effect on effectiveness is: $T3'$ has to go up ($T3' > T3$) because it has to deliver quanta to all other ports. $T1'$ has to go down ($T1' < T1$) because it receives quanta from all other ports. And $T2'$ probably goes down as well ($T2' < T2$) because it normally receives less quanta from port 3 than it has to deliver to port 4 and 1. As a result, the real effectiveness goes down compared to the effectiveness of the “Shannon Isentropic heat exchanger” because the numerator does not change a lot while the denominator goes up. As a result a real heat exchanger shows a kind of maximum and will reduce performance significantly at lower mass-flows.

Just as we cannot make an isentropic turbine, we are not able to build a "Shannon Isentropic heat exchanger", and certainly not better. The area above the Shannon $H=0$ case does not exist.

The BOSAL heat exchanger typically reaches effectiveness values of 90% at $z=1$. Expressed in quality factor this turns out to be around $(k.A/G)=1200$. This is a non-dimensional quantity factor. Later we will discuss a method to measure this quality factor accurately.

What are the parameters that influence the quality factor $(k.A/G)$? In general, the relative thermal resistance of the thermal bridges over the structured core must be as big as possible. This relative thermal resistance of the thermal bridges reflects all what can go wrong such as:

- Temperature gradient (dT/dx) along foils, not perpendicular to surface A
 - Choice of foil: highly alloyed material grade (austenitic and inconels)
 - Choice of foil: thickness in microns instead of millimeters
- Non-uniformity flows that deviate from balanced counterflow, cause heat exchange and mixing at higher different temperatures
- By-pass flow
- Thermal bridges between core/manifolds under different temperatures
- Radiation hot zones towards cold zones $T^4(\text{hot})-T^4(\text{cold})$ (internal)
- Insulation between the manifolds and ducting
- Heat exchange in wedges (cross-flow type zone) at bigger temperature differences
- Manufacturing (tolerances, expertise and accomplishment)
- ...

Performance Charts of Real Heat Exchangers at Different z Value

In the same way, for each z -value, the reduction of the performance can be plotted starting from the curve of the "Shannon Isentropic heat exchanger" on the top. This is done for Z values deviating from 1. Graphs are plotted, one for z -value lower than one and one for higher than one. Also here, the zone in the graph above the "Shannon Isentropic heat exchanger"-curve does not exist.

Until now we spoke about heating up the cold flow. Cooling down of the hot flow could also be the aim, to reach a certain temperature window for the process downstream of the hot outlet. This can be handled in the same way. More than that, only a small set of graphs is needed. One can speak about a set of mirrored graphs.

Considering heating up the cold flow, the effectiveness gives the degree how close the target, hot inlet temperature is reached. Considering cooling down the hot flow, the effectiveness gives the degree how close the target, cold inlet temperature, is reached.

Figure 9. Mirrored graphs with $z=0.6$.

Figure 10. Mirrored graphs with $z=1.0$.

Figure 11. Mirrored graphs with $z=1.66$.

In case $z=1$, the first law of thermodynamics is the reason why the same graph can be applied on the hot side, interpreting this graph as the NTU determined on the hot side mass-flow and hot side c_p and the target is the cold inlet temperature. Because the graph only contains non-dimensional parameters, we end up with two identical graphs. If we reach 100%, the hot flow will fully reach the cold inlet temperature. When we now reduce the quality factor, $k.A/G$, the same reasoning holds for the hot side. So we can also use the same graph to determine the effect of the quality factor for the hot side.

In case $z < 1$, there is more than sufficient heat available to reach high effectiveness values on the cold side. This situation is discussed in detail before. By reaching effectiveness values up to 100% cause a kind of saturation effect that stops the heat transfer which results in a high hot outlet temperature. This results in a low effectiveness value on the hot side. Due to the First Law of Thermodynamics we can prove that the graph of $1/z$ yields for the hot side, not only for the “Shannon Isentropic heat exchanger” but also for lower quality cases. Here it is important to use the hot side mass-flow and c_p to

determine the X-value. In this way you can see that the maxima in the graph of course fit with the maxima in the other graph, according to the FLT.

In case $z > 1$, the same reasoning can be applied which leads to only 3 different graphs to describe the behavior of the cold and the hot flow for 3 cases of z and 6 cases of the quality factor ($k.A/G$). All these cases are visualized in figure 9 to 11. All these parameters are non-dimensional and this model can thus be used for any gas composition going from air, exhaust, CO, hydrogen or any combination.

Microturbulences and Reynolds Dependent Heat Transfer

The reciprocal value of NTU is proportional to the massflow when $k.A$ is constant. This is the laminar case. When microturbulences enhance the heat transfer, $k.A$ is a function of the Reynolds number to a certain power γ . One can still use the graphs we discussed before by projecting the massflow axis on the $1/NTU$ axis in a double logarithmic graph. When γ is zero, $1/NTU$ is proportional to the massflow, when γ is one, the whole massflow axis is projected to one point on the $1/NTU$ scale, resulting in a singularity.

Figure 12. Microturbulences and Reynolds dependent heat transfer.

Curve Fitting Technique on Test Results

We have now a model available based on five non-dimensional parameters: effectiveness, z , NTU, $k.A/G$ and γ . One can determine effectiveness and z by

- a) measuring the cold and hot mass-flow,
- b) determine the c_p values of the cold and hot flows and
- c) measure the temperatures on the real heat exchanger.

Use this input to apply curve fitting to find the best fit for NTU, $k.A/G$ and γ in the three dimensional space to determine not only on the value of the effectiveness but also on its curvature.

This exercise is done for the BOSAL laser-welded solution in comparison with a brazed solution of a competitor. The exercise reveals that the quality factor of the BOSAL unit (quality=1204[-]) is more than five times higher as the competitor unit (quality=209[-]). This is realized based on better selection of a list of parameters mentioned in the next figure.

Figure 13. Comparison between laser-welded and vacuum-brazed solution.

There is a sizing calculator available on www.ECI.BOSAL.com based on this modeling with five non-dimensional parameters, k.A/G, gamma, z, NTU and effectiveness. Because these parameters are non-dimensional, this model can thus be used for any gas composition going from air, exhaust, H₂O, CO₂, CO, hydrogen or any other combination.

Generalization of theory towards catalytic active Hot-BoP components

We considered until now the temperature and entropy as the driving forces in the processes in the Hot-BoP component. Parallel to these processes and fundamentals, a similar logic or reasoning can be applied on the chemical conversions and their thermodynamic equilibria.

The catalysis material is used to accelerate the kinetics of the reaction to achieve the Thermodynamic Equilibrium of the redox reactions. Also here, as Shannon posed, nature will strive to make the amount of disorder as large as possible. In this case the Gibbs Free Energy (GFE) is applied. In practice, for such reaction descriptions one looks for the minima of the GFE which is based on maximizing the amount of disorder defined as

$$-\Delta g = T \cdot \Delta s - \Delta h$$

The minus sign makes maximizing the Shannon Entropy similar as minimizing the Gibbs Free Energy. Also here, an ordered energy quantum management is required to get optimal usage of the energy flow. Creating the favourable conditions, such as the temperature and pressure windows, the energy quanta will disappear as thermal quanta and will appear as converted fuel, containing higher combustion value. So the reasoning is similar as we applied with the heat exchangers, only the scale to put the quanta on, differ. It is more an enthalpy scale as a temperature scale.

To realize this, BOSAL developed catalytic coated heat exchangers, one side coated for reductive, endothermal reactions to transform fuels, the other side with oxidative coatings to achieve optimal composition of exhaust gasses or facilitation of start-up processes.

Heat exchangers with integrated mixer are available which are designed in such a way that the mixture is within 3 milliseconds in the vicinity of the heat exchanging surface, to achieve a controlled temperature of the metal.

Figure 14 Picture of integrated mixer

Conclusion

Until now the description of the quality of counter-flow heat exchangers was mainly based on effectiveness and First Law of Thermodynamics. Effectiveness showed out to be a confusing quality parameter. Involving the Second Law of Thermodynamics and especially the Shannon 1948 entropy reveals a deeper look into the heat exchanger and its description. The definition of the “Shannon Isentropic heat exchanger” in combination with a quality factor $k.A/G$ gives an unambiguous way to characterize a real counter-flow heat exchanger. A test method and curve fitting technique in a multi-dimensional space with 5 non-dimensional parameters offers an accurate method to quantify the involved parameters, which can be used by any gas composition. Such components can be applied in SOFC, SOEC and r-SOC for stationary and mobile applications.

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